

ONLINE LEARNING: PROS AND CONS, RECOMMENDED WAYS TO MAKE IT EASIER

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Abstract: In the developed and developing world now, there are tons of ways for learning particular skill. This article research will reveal some advantages and disadvantages of online learning. Besides, we will illustrate some ways for students who have difficulty in learning online but no time or effort for offline learning.

Key words: online learning, university life, discomfort, books, podcasts, e-books, records, videos, pictures.

Introduction

Nowadays online learning turns out to be more and more practiced. Many traditional universities started to share their courses online for free. It represents an easy and comfortable method to achieve knowledge in almost every field, from law and accounting, to human sciences, such as psychology and sociology or history. Online learning is a great alternative to traditional universities, especially for people who cannot afford the time and money to take real courses.

Let's look at the advantages of online learning. Although many people still consider traditional universities as the best way to achieve knowledge and get a diploma, online learning proves to be a great alternative. Students have the chance to study in their own time and especially for free. It represents a great way to study many fields and to boost the level of self-motivation. Online learning is so effective because students can finish their homework quickly, and there is more time left for hobbies or for finding a job.

An access to all resources of a traditional course helps participants learn wherever they are, leaving them the freedom to choose the time for study. With basically an Internet connection, a person can attend different courses. Among the advantages of online learning there are the responsibility and self-discipline of students.

Next advantage is efficiency. Online learning offers teachers an efficient way to deliver lessons to students. Online learning has a number of tools such as videos, PDFs, podcasts, and teachers can use all these tools as part of their lesson plans. By extending the lesson plan beyond traditional textbooks to include online resources, teachers are able to become more efficient educators.

Another advantage of online education is that it allows students to attend classes from any location of their choice. It also allows schools to reach out to a more extensive network of students, instead of being restricted by geographical boundaries. Additionally, online lectures can be recorded, archived, and shared for future reference. This allows students to access the learning material at a time of their comfort.

Thus, online learning offers students the accessibility of time and place in education.

Online education is far more affordable as compared to physical learning. This is because online learning eliminates the cost points of student transportation, student meals, and most importantly, real estate. Additionally, all the course or study materials are available online,

thus creating a paperless learning environment, which is more affordable, while also being beneficial to the environment.

We might cover plenty of advantages of online learning because so far educational professionals find tons of effective ways for online learning, which we mentioned above some of them. Now it is time for disadvantages of online learning for individuals:

For many students, one of the biggest challenges of online learning is the struggle with focusing on the screen for long periods of time. With online learning, there is also a greater chance for students to be easily distracted by social media or other sites. Therefore, it is imperative for the teachers to keep their online classes crisp, engaging, and interactive to help students stay focused on the lesson.

Another key challenge of online classes is internet connectivity. While internet penetration has grown in leaps and bounds over the past few years, in smaller cities and towns, a consistent connection with decent speed is a problem. Without a consistent internet connection for students or teachers, there can be a lack of continuity in learning for the child. This is detrimental to the education process.

Students can learn a lot from being in the company of their peers. However, in an online class, there are minimal physical interactions between students and teachers. This often results in a sense of isolation for the students. In this situation, it is imperative that the school allow for other forms of communication between the students, peers, and teachers. This can include online messages, emails and video conferencing that will allow for face-to-face interaction and reduce the sense of isolation.

Moreover, some adults and young students may find it difficult to understand the topic properly, because as we know in online classes, time is restricted and in the middle of the class zoom session may end or the connection interrupted. While in face to face classes people could ask as much questions as possible or they might sit after the class and do their homework.

Despite of the significant advantages of e-learning, students encounter several challenges which ultimately lead towards either limited or negative outcomes. Such as; Arkorful and Abaidoo (2015) in their study outlined that e-learning, in certain cases is held through remoteness and contemplation resulting in lack of student's interaction. In comparison with the contemporary mode of education, e-learning might result in being less effective due to the absence of face to face encounter with instructions or teachers. Since in e-learning method, assessments are generally held online which reduces the possibility of restricting illegitimate activities such as; cheating, plagiarism etc (Arkorful and Abaidoo, 2015). The absence of essential personal interactions is the most noticeable drawback of e-learning, not only among colleague learners, but also between instructors and learners (Islam, Beer and Slack, 2015). There is a scarcity of community in the online learning environment as student-student engagement is much less of a concern when compared with student-instructor interaction. Gilbert (2015) highlighted that most of the students wish to work autonomously to avoid the need to interact with their classmates. Cultural barrier is another important disadvantage of introducing an online course. Aparicio, Bacao and Oliveira, (2016) in their study evaluated the influence of cultural characteristics which includes individualism and collectivism in determining the perceived success of elearning. Findings of the study indicated a significant influence of individualism and collectivism on organizational and individual impacts.

Technology is a platform that can be easily acquired for granted when it is engaged into daily life, but it is not widely used because of the lack of monetary benefits for achieving access. The global knowledge available on the internet is led by increasing the proportion of computers and other electronic devices to students (Talebian, Mohammadi and Rezvanfar, 2014). Another disadvantage is maintaining motivation in an online course that online learners experience. Students who lack self-motivation and independence had reduced success rates as compared to their counterparts (Sarkar, 2012). Learners that lack self-regulation have a tendency to not assign sufficient time for completing assignments; therefore, switching in poor quality work or late assignments. Overall, successful students have stronger beliefs that they will succeed, better technology skills and access, higher self-responsibility, and higher self-organization skills (Sarrab, Al-Shihi and Rehman, 2013). Students must be able to assess the motivating factors to continue the momentum throughout the duration of the course. Students lack motivation and can easily lose sight of their original objective, rapidly become lost within the course, and consequently withdraw from the course (Raspopovic et al., 2017). Therefore, it is pertinent to determine the success of an individual to undertake an online course by understanding learning styles and self-behaviour.

Conclusion

E-learning is an effective tool to transfer knowledge and it has the potential for overtaking the conventional teaching method. E-learning training help learners and instructors in educational environment. Students' needs are becoming priority for instructors and; thus, universities and colleges are implementing e-learning system in their own training programs. Through the study findings, it has been identified that e-learning has been advantageous to its users in many ways. One of the most dominant characteristics of e-learning is that it ensures ease of communication between teachers and students, and contributes in developing students' skills. It further contributes in providing scientific material to students in an interesting manner. In contrast to this, e-learning has developed negative influence on students as it promotes social isolation due to increase in screen time.

The study has concluded that students prefer to use e-learning since it provides chances to enhance their learning and increase their abilities. On the contrary, the support of e-learning is not adequate for assuring the advantages for effective learning students to socially interact with their fellowship and mentors during their academic year. In particular, there is an actual need for a well-established e-learning environment, which learners and instructors can rely on. E-learning will become more popular to make the users feel secure and comfortable with the complement of instructors and mentors. Future studies are required on a larger scale, including additional online courses, professors, and students to better assess the advantages, disadvantages, and useful strategies of successful students.

References:

1. [https://elearningindustry.com/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-online-learning/amp](https://elearningindustry.com/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-online-learning/)
2. Alaa Zuhir Al Rawashdeh, Enaam Youssef Mohammed¹, Asma Rebhi Al Arab¹, Mahmoud Alara⁴ and Butheyra Al-Rawashdeh² ¹Ajman University, Ajman, UAE Al Balqaa Applied University, Jordan Ain-Shamd University, Egypt Clemson University, USA. Advantages and Disadvantages of Using e-Learning in University Education: Analyzing Students' Perspectives.